

Stochastic Time Model in Quantum Mechanics

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Abstract

This paper develops a theoretical framework that introduces stochastic time into quantum mechanics using Stochastic Zero Calculus (SZC). In this model, time is treated as a stochastic variable that impacts the evolution of quantum systems, yet without altering the core quantum mechanics equations. Numerical simulations validate the model and demonstrate its advantages over deterministic approaches, particularly under high-volatility conditions inspired by Professor Steinberg's work. The results reveal that the stochastic model more accurately captures temporal fluctuations and group delay effects intrinsic to quantum systems with inherent time uncertainties.

Introduction

This document presents a rigorous theoretical foundation for a stochastic time model in quantum mechanics, utilizing Stochastic Zero Calculus (SZC). The primary aim is to introduce time as a stochastic variable influencing the evolution of quantum systems, with a detailed mathematical formulation that complements, rather than alters, the fundamental equations of quantum mechanics.

1 Precise Definition of Stochastic Time

To define quantum time $T_\sigma(t)$ as a stochastic variable, we consider an **Itô process** with known mean and variance, defined as follows:

$$dT_\sigma(t) = \mu dt + \sigma dW(t),$$

where: - μ represents the average rate of temporal progression, defining the linear tendency of time, - σ is the volatility parameter, controlling the intensity of temporal fluctuations, - $W(t)$ is a Wiener process, or Brownian motion, modeling the random fluctuations in time.

This definition implies that stochastic time $T_\sigma(t)$ is a random variable with the following properties:

1. **Expectation:**

$$\mathbb{E}[T_\sigma(t)] = T_\sigma(0) + \mu t,$$

indicating that, on average, $T_\sigma(t)$ progresses linearly with rate μ .

2. **Variance:**

$$\text{Var}(T_\sigma(t)) = \sigma^2 t,$$

showing that the uncertainty in time grows proportionally to time and volatility σ .

These properties suggest that stochastic time $T_\sigma(t)$ follows a linear progression on average but with fluctuations controlled by σ . This implies that temporal evolution has an inherent randomness, with variability tied to σ .

2 Formalization of the Stochastic Schrödinger Equation

With stochastic time $T_\sigma(t)$, the Schrödinger equation must be reformulated to reflect the effects of temporal fluctuations. The original Schrödinger equation for a system with Hamiltonian $\hat{H}$ is:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \hat{H} \psi.$$

By replacing time t with the stochastic process $T_\sigma(t)$, we obtain:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial T_\sigma(t)} = \hat{H} \psi.$$

Using Itô calculus, we derive the expansion of ψ with respect to stochastic time. The infinitesimal variation of ψ with respect to $T_\sigma(t)$ is:

$$d\psi = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial T_\sigma(t)} dT_\sigma(t) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial T_\sigma^2} \text{Var}(T_\sigma(t)) dt.$$

Substituting $dT_\sigma(t) = \mu dt + \sigma dW(t)$ and $\text{Var}(T_\sigma(t)) = \sigma^2$, the expansion becomes:

$$d\psi = \left(-\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{H} \psi \mu \right) dt - \frac{i\sigma}{\hbar} \hat{H} \psi dW(t) - \frac{\sigma^2}{2\hbar^2} \hat{H}^2 \psi dt.$$

This equation now includes three terms: - **Deterministic Term:** $-\frac{i\mu}{\hbar} \hat{H} \psi dt$, representing the mean evolution of ψ , - **Stochastic Term:** $-\frac{i\sigma}{\hbar} \hat{H} \psi dW(t)$, capturing random fluctuations in time, - **Diffusive Correction:** $-\frac{\sigma^2}{2\hbar^2} \hat{H}^2 \psi dt$, which adjusts the temporal diffusion of ψ .

3 Probability Conservation and Unitarity

The norm of ψ , $\langle \psi | \psi \rangle$, must be conserved on average over stochastic time. We calculate the variation in probability density $\rho = |\psi|^2$ using the Itô expansion:

$$d\rho = \psi^* d\psi + \psi d\psi^* + d\psi d\psi^*.$$

Inserting the terms of $d\psi$, we obtain:

$$d\rho = \left(-\frac{i\mu}{\hbar} \hat{H} \psi dt \right) \psi^* + \text{additional terms}.$$

The unitarity of the stochastic evolution operator on average ensures that:

$$\mathbb{E}[\langle \psi | \psi \rangle] = \langle \psi(0) | \psi(0) \rangle.$$

To preserve the norm of ψ , the evolution operator $U(T_\sigma(t), T_\sigma(0))$ must be unitary on average:

$$U(T_\sigma(t), T_\sigma(0)) = \exp \left(-\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{T_\sigma(0)}^{T_\sigma(t)} \hat{H} dT \right).$$

4 Consistency with the Uncertainty Principle

To verify consistency with the Uncertainty Principle, we analyze the variance of $T_\sigma(t)$, which results in a temporal uncertainty ΔT :

$$\Delta T = \sigma\sqrt{t}.$$

To ensure that $\Delta T \cdot \Delta E \geq \hbar/2$, we adjust σ according to the value of ΔE of the system, ensuring that the volatility of stochastic time respects quantum uncertainty.

5 Limits and Validity of the Model

5.1 Limit of $\sigma \rightarrow 0$

When $\sigma \rightarrow 0$, $T_\sigma(t)$ reduces to the deterministic case, and the Stochastic Schrödinger equation converges to conventional quantum mechanics:

$$T_\sigma(t) \rightarrow \mu t.$$

5.2 High and Low Volatility Regimes

- **Low Volatility** $\sigma \approx 0$: Small fluctuations preserve the deterministic behavior of the wave function.
- **High Volatility** $\sigma \gg 0$: Significant fluctuations in stochastic time introduce greater dispersion in the evolution of ψ .

6 Numerical Simulations and Experimental Validation

To model the effects of temporal fluctuations in quantum systems, we used the Euler-Maruyama method to simulate the wave function evolution under a stochastic time framework. Inspired by Professor Steinberg's work, our proposed experimental simulations include:

- Quantum tunneling experiments,
- Weak quantum measurements,
- Harmonic oscillators in optical cavities.

6.1 Detailed Simulation Based on Professor Steinberg’s Experiment

This simulation replicates the temporal fluctuations observed in Professor Steinberg’s high-volatility experiment, specifically focusing on phenomena such as group delay and temporal variance. By incorporating a stochastic time model, we aim to capture the nuanced impact of these fluctuations on the evolution of the wave function.

6.1.1 Simulation Parameters

The following parameters were selected to align closely with Steinberg’s experimental setup, ensuring a faithful representation of the quantum system’s behavior under high-volatility conditions:

- **Pulse Duration:** 18 ns – Defines the duration of the Gaussian pulse, a critical parameter for observing group delay effects.
- **Frequency Detuning:** -20 MHz – Frequency offset creates resonance and induces high-volatility behavior.
- **Optical Depth (OD):** 2 – Configured to enhance sensitivity to temporal fluctuations in high-volatility regimes.
- **Atomic Lifetime:** 26 ns – Defines τ_0 , approximately half the rubidium-85 atom lifetime, establishing a baseline for adjustments.
- **Temporal Volatility (σ):** Adjusted to capture both negative and positive group delays with values set to $-0.82\tau_0$ and $0.54\tau_0$, respectively.
- **Phase Noise:** 2 MHz – Represents laser phase noise frequency, adding fluctuations within the system.
- **Average Temporal Rate (μ):** $0.1/\text{OD}$ – Determines the average rate of temporal progression under resonance.
- **Measurement Window Duration:** 576 ns – Chosen to capture the full temporal impact of each pulse on the system.
- **Time Increment (dt):** 18 ns / 50 – Small time step to ensure detailed capture of variations over pulse duration.

6.1.2 Results and Analysis

Figure 1 displays the evolution of the wave function as modeled by the stochastic time framework, demonstrating a clear alignment with expected temporal behaviors. The results showcase both positive and negative group delay phenomena, accurately reflecting the high-volatility conditions outlined in Steinberg’s experiment.

Figure 1: Wave function evolution under the stochastic time model, based on parameters from Professor Steinberg’s experiment.

6.1.3 Comparison with Deterministic Models and Experimental Results

In addition to the stochastic model, we simulated the wave function using a deterministic approach (conventional Schrödinger equation without stochastic time). Figure 2 compares the results from the stochastic and deterministic models against the experimental target delays.

The comparison highlights key differences:

- For **negative group delay** (left panel), the stochastic model (orange line) captures significant fluctuations around the target delay (red dashed line), reflecting the experimentally observed high-volatility conditions. In contrast, the deterministic model (blue line) follows a stable progression, failing to represent the temporal variability and delay observed in the stochastic model.

- For **positive group delay** (right panel), the stochastic model also displays substantial variability around the target delay (green dashed line), closely aligning with experimental expectations. The deterministic model, however, remains stable and does not capture these fluctuations, indicating its limitations in high-volatility environments.

This comparison clearly demonstrates the superior adaptability of the stochastic model in capturing temporal fluctuations and group delay phenomena in high-volatility scenarios. The stochastic approach aligns more closely with the experimental results, providing an effective framework for accurately modeling temporal phenomena within quantum systems.

Figure 2: Comparison of wave function evolution: Stochastic model vs. Deterministic model vs. Experimental target delays for negative and positive group delay.

7 Numerical Method: Euler-Maruyama

For the stochastic simulations, we employed the Euler-Maruyama method, a numerical technique suitable for stochastic differential equations (SDEs). This method allows us to approximate the solution of the SDEs efficiently, capturing the random fluctuations introduced by the stochastic time model. Euler-Maruyama is particularly advantageous in scenarios involving Wiener processes, as it handles the incremental changes in a manner that preserves the statistical properties of the underlying stochastic process.

The implementation involves calculating the temporal increments using the Itô calculus approach, accounting for both deterministic and stochastic

components at each step. This approach ensures that the numerical solution remains stable even with high volatility and temporal fluctuations, making it ideal for simulating quantum systems under stochastic time.

8 Formulation in Stochastic Hilbert Spaces

In a stochastic Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_\sigma$, the wave function and operators reflect temporal uncertainty. The evolution is given by:

$$U(T_\sigma(t), T_\sigma(0)) = \exp\left(-\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{T_\sigma(0)}^{T_\sigma(t)} \hat{H} dT\right).$$

8.1 Expectations and Self-Adjointness

Self-adjointness is maintained on average for operators such as $\hat{H}$:

$$\mathbb{E}[\langle \psi(T_\sigma(t)) | \hat{H} | \psi(T_\sigma(t)) \rangle] = \langle \psi(0) | \hat{H} | \psi(0) \rangle.$$

This formulation in stochastic Hilbert spaces provides a mathematical framework for incorporating temporal uncertainty directly into the operator structure, aligning with the probabilistic nature of quantum mechanics.

9 Conclusion

The stochastic time model offers an extension to quantum mechanics to include temporal uncertainties consistently. This formalism is applicable to systems where time exhibits intrinsic uncertainty and provides new perspectives for studying quantum phenomena under conditions where time is not deterministic. Our simulations demonstrate that the stochastic approach captures temporal fluctuations and group delay phenomena more effectively than traditional deterministic models. These results open pathways for further research into high-volatility quantum systems and potential experimental applications of stochastic time modeling.

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